

Research protocol

From Research to Resilience: Preparedness Lessons from COVID-19

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Research protocol

This document presents the research protocol outlining the approach to deliver the SARS-CoV-2 sequencing grants reflection.

1. Background and introduction

In response to the emerging SARS-CoV-2 variants of concern, Wellcome funded ten principal investigators to establish a consortium of labs to enable SARS-CoV-2 pathogen genomic sequencing and surveillance. The majority of these awards were funded between January and September 2021. A critical aim of these projects was to ensure the rapid uptake and sharing of genomic sequence data and analyses into decision-making processes.

Whilst this coupling of evidence generation to decision-making is sought after and encouraged, less is understood about how other components of the research environment enable or hinder this. Within this context, Wellcome sees its portfolio of SARS-CoV-2 sequencing grants as a unique opportunity to learn about these issues from projects which are similar in scope but operate in very different contexts. These grants were issued as part of a tranche of funding released by Wellcome, part of which was set aside for the genomic surveillance projects that are within the scope of this review. These projects were part of an emergency funding call focusing on research projects in Africa and Asia.

Research Consulting was commissioned by Wellcome to investigate the ten funded projects through two phases of work taking place between August 2023 and October 2024. Phase 1 focused on investigating three projects, while Phase 2 focused on engaging with the remaining seven projects. This work has aimed to address three key objectives:

- Understand pathways to data generation, sharing and decision-making within different local and regional contexts
- Learn about hidden and unaccounted for processes from the diverse research community
- Identify solutions to address the challenges faced by researchers in different contexts

This research has supported the development of a final report and evidence base that can be used to inform and improve Wellcome's approach to emergency funding in the future

2. Understanding the research protocol

The work outlined above has been delivered through desk research and consultations with key stakeholders. This research protocol presents a methodology to conduct the necessary activities that can be replicated across funded projects.

This document provides an overview of the key stages involved in delivering stakeholder consultations as well as a detailed outline of activities associated with each stage. For each stage of the project, a description of key activities is provided. For each activity, key dependencies and outputs are defined and owners and contributors are assigned. Where activities differ between Phase 1 and Phase 2, this is noted in the table text.

Throughout the document and the figures included, responsibilities are colour-coded as follows: **Research Consulting**, **Wellcome**, **project participants** (e.g. funded-project team members), and **in-country associates**.

2.1 Protocol overview

The diagram below provides an overview of key activities involved in project delivery for Phases 1 and 2. Key project deliverables are indicated using **bold text**.

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Stage 1. Understanding the in-scope projects

Activity	Description	Dependencies	Outputs	Owner	Contributor
1a. Secure documentation from Wellcome	Obtain relevant project-related documents to support analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ability to share information in line with Wellcome's confidentiality guidelines 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project document pack including funding applications, funding timeline, and progress reports 	Wellcome	-
1b. Develop project summary document	Prepare a project summary document, outlining key aims, objectives and outcomes of in-scope projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Level of detail and accuracy provided in documentation held by Wellcome 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project summary documents of in-scope projects 	Research Consulting	Associates
1c. Develop initial stakeholder list	Review project summary documents and gather names to create a longlist of stakeholders. Complete list with contact details through additional desk research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Level of detail provided in documentation held by Wellcome 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Longlist of stakeholders by project in Excel format 	Research Consulting	Associates
1d. Develop supporting documents for PI interviews	Develop an interview pack for Principal Investigators (PIs) including interview briefing note, interview question set, consent form, and slide deck supporting introductory PI calls	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Level of detail provided in documentation held by Wellcome 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interview briefing note Interview question set Consent form Slide deck 	Research Consulting	-
1e. Introduce project team to Principal Investigators	Secure an introduction to PIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introductory text provided by Research Consulting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Email invitations shared with PIs 	Wellcome	Research Consulting
1f. Conduct introductory calls with Principal Investigators	Schedule interviews with PIs to review project aims and objectives, supported by slide deck developed in Stage 1d	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Availability of PIs to contribute to calls 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Transcripts of conversations with PIs 	Research Consulting	Associates
1g. Conduct interview with Wellcome team to understand funding context	Schedule interviews with Wellcome team members who were involved in developing the emergency funding call	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Availability of Wellcome staff to contribute to calls 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Transcripts of conversations with Wellcome team 	Research Consulting	Wellcome

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Stage 2. Development of key project documentation

Activity	Description	Dependencies	Outputs	Owner	Contributor
2a. Complete initial desk research to inform key project documentation	Undertake a desk research exercise to inform the development of the team briefing document and analytical framework	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Time availability and accessibility of key project documents 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Desk research methodology and results of desk research exercise to inform key project documentation 	Research Consulting	Associates
2b. Develop interview questions and briefing documents	Develop interview questions that address the research objectives of the project and build on the conversations with PIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contributions from PIs during initial conversations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interview question sets for project team members, interviewer briefs and notes templates 	Research Consulting	Research Consulting Associates
2c. Develop project team internal briefing document	Develop a briefing document to inform the team of project objectives and key stages of the data generation, sharing and uptake pathway	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Team briefing document 	Research Consulting	Research Consulting Associates
2d. Develop analytical framework to inform analysis	Develop analytical framework to inform analysis of desk research and stakeholder engagement findings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contributions from PIs during initial interviews Findings from desk research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analytical framework including proposed themes for thematic analysis of project findings 	Research Consulting	Research Consulting Associates
2e. Develop consultation protocol	Develop consultation protocol outlining approach to each project stage, key activities, dependencies, outputs, owners and contributors	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research protocol in Word format for revision following initiation of future phases of work 	Research Consulting	Research Consulting Associates
2f. Develop country-level landscape maps for each project	Develop initial landscape maps based on calls with PIs, initial interview findings and responses to online survey to highlight key relationships and information flows within projects.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sufficient information gathered from consultations and online survey 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Landscape maps for each project 	Research Consulting	Associates

NOTES: Desk research (Stage 2a) follows the Quick Scoping Review methodology (UK Government, 2015). Details of this methodology are outlined in the desk research methodology document. Interview briefing notes and question sets have been developed following best-practice for semi-structured interviews (Adeoye-Olatunde, 2021). This includes developing a succinct question set that addresses the research objectives, while allowing the interviewer to explore pertinent issues as they are raised by interviewees. The project's analytical framework has been developed to inform qualitative coding, following the methodology outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006).

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Stage 3. Stakeholder identification and interview invitations

Activity	Description	Dependencies	Outputs	Owner	Contributor
3a. Identify stakeholders for invitation to first round of interviews	Principal investigators to review stakeholder list and provide suggestions for initial interviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Updates provided by PIs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Revised stakeholder list with recommendations for initial interviews 	Project participants	Research Consulting
3b. Allocate stakeholders to interviewers on the project team	Research Consulting to review stakeholder list, allocate a lead interviewer and develop plan for in-person or virtual interviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Updates provided by PIs to understand interviewee locations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Detailed stakeholder list including allocation of interviewers and notes on in-person versus virtual interviews 	Research Consulting	-
3c. Develop travel plans to support in-person interviews	Lead interviewers to develop travel plans to support in-person interviews including details on vaccination/visa requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Updates provided by PIs to understand interviewee locations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Travel plans and visit schedule for sharing with appropriate team members 	Research Consulting	Associates Research Consulting
3d. Invite stakeholders to interviews	Research Consulting to invite stakeholders to interview following PI recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recommendations from PIs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Invitations to interview to priority stakeholders 	Research Consulting	Project participants
3e. Arrange interviews with selected stakeholders	Associates to arrange interviews with selected stakeholders based on location	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coordination from Research Consulting Availability of interviewees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scheduled meetings with selected funded-project stakeholders 	Research Consulting Associates	Research Consulting
3f. Identify participants for second round of engagement (interviews or focus groups)	Interviewers to gather additional names from interviewees to identify other stakeholders for participation in interviews or focus groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Response rates of secondary interviewees and gaps remaining from first round of interviews 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Updated stakeholder list with recommendations from interviewees 	Research Consulting Associates	-
3g. Assign stakeholders to relevant engagement type	Research Consulting to review stakeholder longlist and assign names to categories e.g. participation in interview, focus group, or no engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development of proposed sampling approach for interviews and focus groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Updated longlist of stakeholders for potential contributions to validation focus groups 	Research Consulting	Associates

NOTES: Stakeholders involved in this project are primarily identified through three routes:

- introductions to principal investigators from Wellcome (Stage 1e),

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- identification of project team members through a review of grant documentation and introductions from principal investigators (**Stages 1c**); and
- snowball sampling through recommendations or referrals from engaged project stakeholders or associates (**Stage 3f**).

Stage 4. Consultation delivery

Activity	Description	Dependencies	Outputs	Owner	Contributor
4a. Conduct semi-structured interviews with shortlisted interviewees	Associates and Research Consulting to conduct semi-structured interviews, following the agreed interview questionnaire format and following semi-structured interview best practices (see Section 2 notes)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of project stakeholders to participate • Reliability of internet connection • Availability of facilities to meet interviewees in person • Availability of interviewees for possible in-person interviews 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interviews with selected funded-project stakeholders 	<p>Research Consulting</p> <p>Associates</p>	-
4b. Share landscape maps with PIs and interviewees	Share landscape maps with PIs and interviewees to confirm relationships and information flows within projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ability of PIs and interviewees to confirm relationships mapped 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validated landscape maps for each project 	<p>Research Consulting</p> <p>Associates</p>	
4c. Share transcripts and recordings with project team	Associates and Research Consulting to share interview recordings and notes to a shared folder. Research Consulting will run recordings through Otter (AI transcription software) to generate transcripts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Timely sharing of interview recordings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interview transcripts and interviewer notes 	<p>Research Consulting</p> <p>Associates</p>	-
4d. Record stakeholders identified for survey distribution	Interviewers to ask interviewees to recommend individuals* to complete our survey and capture this information in the stakeholder longlist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interviewees providing names for potential survey respondents 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • List of potential survey respondents 	<p>Research Consulting</p> <p>Associates</p>	-
4e. Prepare focus group materials and deliver sessions	Phase 2 only: Invite select stakeholders to focus groups, following the process outlined for interviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of team members to participate in focus groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus group materials and mixed focus groups with project participants 	<p>Research Consulting</p>	Associates

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4f. Conduct stakeholder focus groups	Phase 2 only: Conduct four focus groups with project teams to validate emerging findings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of participants to join focus groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus groups with project participants 	Research Consulting	Associates
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* In **Stage 4d**, we propose to adopt a snowball sampling approach, to identify a broad range of stakeholders and to capture a wide sample of the research community, beyond the core groups engaged via interviews and focus groups. This is likely to include technicians, project managers, individuals in research support roles and policy experts.

Stage 5. Survey design and distribution

Stage 5: Survey design and distribution					
Activity	Description	Dependencies	Outputs	Owner	Contributor
5a. Design survey questions	Develop online survey to (i) gather quantitative data to support prioritisation of issues identified in qualitative research (ii) gather input from a broader range of stakeholders than reached via interviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion with Wellcome team to refine aims of online survey 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online survey draft in Alchemer or preferred survey platform 	Research Consulting	Associates Wellcome
5b. Review, test and finalise survey	Wellcome and relevant colleagues to test survey and provide feedback for Research Consulting to implement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of Wellcome team to review online survey 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reviewed survey implemented in survey platform • Finalised online survey question set 	Research Consulting	Wellcome
5c. Distribute survey to all stakeholders that have completed interviews	Distribute survey to relevant project team members following their interviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responses of team members already engaged in interviews 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online survey distributed to in-scope projects 	Research Consulting	Research Consulting Associates
5d. Distribute survey to stakeholders recommended by interviewees	Distribute survey to relevant project team members following recommendations from interviewees	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recommendations from interviewees of team members to complete survey 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online survey distributed to in-scope projects 	Research Consulting	Research Consulting Associates

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Stage 6. Evidence analysis

Activity	Description	Dependencies	Outputs	Owner	Contributor
6a. Conduct thematic coding of interview and focus group findings	Thematic coding of qualitative data according to the analytical framework	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Critical review of coding summaries from in-country associates Updating analytical framework in line with findings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Thematic coding summaries for each project 	Research Consulting	Associates
6b. Conduct qualitative and quantitative survey analysis	Export of survey data for analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sufficient response rate from participants and data quality 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Export of survey responses in anonymised format 	Research Consulting	-
6c. Agree on key messages for reporting	Workshop between consultation leads (Research Consulting and associates) to define key messages from the data and information gathered from interviews and survey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Progress on all projects at a sufficient stage to inform a group workshop 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agreement on key messages for reporting 	Research Consulting	Research Consulting Associates

Stage 7. Landscape mapping and reporting

Activity	Description	Dependencies	Outputs	Owner	Contributor
7a. Update and finalise landscape maps based on feedback from consultations	Prepare final landscape maps following review and contributions from PIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sufficient information gathered from consultations and online survey Feedback and review from PIs and associates 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reviewed landscape maps 	Associates	Research Consulting
7b. Prepare draft findings report to share with Wellcome project team	<p>Phase 1: Prepare summary of key findings and presentation to Wellcome. Prepare Phase 2 report outline</p> <p>Phase 2: Prepare final project report summarising key findings and recommendations for Wellcome</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Key messages emerging from thematic and quantitative analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: Phase 1 report and Phase 2 outline Phase 2: Final project report in draft form for review 	Research Consulting	Research Consulting Associates

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7c. Review draft outputs (final reports and key messages) ahead of reporting	Wellcome to review draft report prepared by Research Consulting and associates, providing any feedback to address in final report	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Availability of Wellcome to review report draft 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: Phase 1 report and Phase 2 outline Phase 2: Final project report in draft form for review 	Wellcome	Wellcome (Senior leaders)
7d. Prepare end of phase report for Wellcome project team	Prepare final report based on feedback from Wellcome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Feedback received from Wellcome 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: Phase 1 report and Phase 2 outline Phase 2: Final project report in draft form for review 	Research Consulting	Associates
7e. Develop communications plan to inform the publication of final outputs	Develop a communications plan highlighting key messages for sharing and dates for publication.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Input from Wellcome comms team to inform the design of infographics or social media tiles and to shape messages for sharing on social media. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communications plan including key messages for public sharing and schedule to inform release of outputs and accompanying messages 	Research Consulting	Wellcome (Comms team)

Stage 8. Revisions to key project documentation

Activity	Description	Dependencies	Outputs	Owner	Contributor
8a. Revise analytical framework*	Research Consulting and in-country associates to revise analytical framework based on Phase 1 evidence-base	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sufficient evidence collected in Phase 1 to inform revised analytical framework 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Revised analytical framework 	Research Consulting	Associates
8b. Revise interview questionnaires*	Research Consulting and in-country associates to revise interview questionnaires based on Phase 1 evidence-base	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sufficient evidence collected in Phase 1 to inform revised interview questionnaires 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Revised interview questionnaires 	Research Consulting	Associates
8c. Revise supporting documentation for interviews*	Research Consulting to revise briefing documents to share with interviewees	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Revised briefing documents for interviewees 	Research Consulting	-
8d. Revise consultation protocol*	Research Consulting to review all stages and activities within the research protocol and revise based on experiences of Phase 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sufficient engagement with Phase 1 to begin future phases of the project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Revised protocol document 	Research Consulting	Associates

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* The continuity of data collection for additional project phases has been considered when updating the analytical framework, interview questions, revise supporting documentation for interviews and protocol.

Stage 9. Data management and publication

Activity	Description	Dependencies	Outputs	Owner	Contributor
9a. Identify documents for internal or external use	Review all project documentation and identify documents for internal and external purposes. This should be done in collaboration with the Wellcome project and communications team.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Availability of Wellcome project and communications team. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> List of documents for internal versus external sharing. 	Research Consulting	Wellcome Wellcome (Comms team)
9b. Prepare external documents for public sharing	Review all documents marked as public-facing to ensure these meet appropriate accessibility criteria and have DOIs where appropriate. Ensure that all project data, including that in the research protocol, that is shared in the public domain is anonymised.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Availability of Wellcome project and communications team. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Set of documents in appropriate formats for public sharing and accompanying DOIs where appropriate. 	Research Consulting	Wellcome Wellcome (Comms team)
9c. Identify appropriate venues for public sharing	Identify appropriate venues for public data sharing in collaboration with the Wellcome project and communications team.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Availability of Wellcome project and communications team. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Set of documents in appropriate formats for public sharing. 	Research Consulting	Wellcome Wellcome (Comms team)
9d. Publish documents according to communications plan	Release public outputs via channels as agreed in communications plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Availability of Wellcome communications team. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Final outputs shared in public domain. 	Wellcome comms team	Research Consulting

Appendix A. Document list

A series of documents supported the delivery of this project – the majority of these being internal, for use by the project team. A list of supporting documents is included below. Those that have been published via Zenodo are **bolded**.

Table 1. Internal documents list.

Name	Description
Project summary: Establishing genomic epidemiology hubs across Latin America	An overview of the Latin America project based on internal documents shared by Wellcome
Project summary: National COVID testing at AAPs	An overview of the AAPs project based on internal documents shared by Wellcome
Project summary: Expansion and support of sequencing in West and Central Africa	An overview of the West and Central Africa project based on internal documents shared by Wellcome
Project summary: Genomic Surveillance Consortium of India and Sri Lanka	An overview of the India and Sri Lanka project based on internal documents shared by Wellcome
Project summary: Epidemic intelligence in South Asia	An overview of the Nepal project based on internal documents shared by Wellcome
Project summary: COVID-19 Genomics - MENA	An overview of the Middle East and North Africa project based on internal documents shared by Wellcome
Stakeholder longlist	A list of names and contact details for all stakeholders identified as part of in-scope projects
Team briefing document	An overview of project objectives and an introduction to genomic sequencing, sharing and uptake for associates

Table 2. External documents list.

Name	Description
Briefing note for Pls	An overview of project objectives and interview format for Pls
Question set for Pls	A set of interview questions for Pls
Interview consent forms	A consent and data protection form for all participants
Pls slide deck	A slide deck to support initial interviews with Pls
Briefing note for interviewees	An overview of project objectives and interview format for project interviewees

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Question set for interviewees	A set of interview questions for project interviewees
Interviewer briefs	Set of interview questions with supporting prompts for interviewers

Table 3. Deliverables list.

Name	Description
Desk research methodology	A document outlining the desk research methodology
Desk research Zotero export	An Excel export of literature used to inform the literature review
Analytical framework	A thematic coding structure to inform analysis of project findings
Research protocol	Proposed research protocol for consultations included in the SARS-CoV-2 sequencing grants reflection
Online survey question set	A Word version of the online survey distributed to project participants
Phase 1 report and Phase 2 outline	Summary of Phase 1 findings with indicative outline for Phase 2 report
Export of online survey responses	Export of online survey responses in anonymised format for sharing
Landscape maps	Attached to final report, mapping out key relationships and information flows across project stakeholders
Executive Summary	Key messages from final report, summarised as an accessible Executive Summary
Final project report	Final report summarising key findings from the individual project consultations and overarching findings
Communications plan	Communications plan highlighting key messages from this work to disseminate across various audiences

Table 4. Project management documents list.

Name	Description
Proposal	Initial project proposal
Addendum to Proposal	Addendum to the initial proposal with updated information on project partners and delivery as requested by Wellcome
Survey scenarios document	An outline of potential options for survey distribution
Travel plans for interviews	An Excel sheet with potential travel plans to support the in-person interviews